

HOW TO BUILT STRONG MEMORY TO LEARN ENGLISH

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Annotation: This article is an integral part of who our memories are but suggestions have been made to reduce our memory and develop memory as we age.

Key words: Strong Memory, new neural connections, make pottery, Mnemonics.

Аннотация: Эта статья является неотъемлемой частью того, что представляет собой наша память, но были высказаны предложения по сокращению нашей памяти и ее развитию с возрастом.

Ключевые слова: Сильная память, новые нейронные связи, изготовление керамики, мнемотехника.

Our memories are an integral part of who we are, but as we age our memory declines. For many older adults, the decline becomes so serious that they're no longer able to live independently, which is one of the biggest fears T trusted Source adults have as they age.

The good news is that scientists have been learning more about our brain's amazing capacity to change and grow new neural connections each day, even in old age. This concept is known as neuroplasticity. Through research on neuroplasticity, scientists have discovered that our memory capacity isn't fixed, but rather malleable like plastic.

Memory strength is just like muscular strength. The more you use it, the stronger it gets. But you can't lift the same size weight every day and expect to get stronger. You'll need to keep your brain constantly challenged. Learning a new skill is an excellent way to strengthen your brain's memory capacity.

There are many activities to choose from, but most importantly, you'll need to find something that forces you out of your comfort zone and commands your full attention.

Here are some examples:

- learn a new instrument
- make pottery
- play mind games, like Sudoku or chess
- learn a new type of dance, like the tango
- learn a new language

Any time you learn a new piece of information, you're more likely to mentally record that information if it's repeated.

Repetition reinforces the connections we create between neurons. Repeat what you hear out loud. Try using it in a sentence. Write it down and read it aloud.

But the work doesn't stop there. Research shows that simple repetition is an ineffective learning tool if used on its own. You'll need to sit back down later and actively try to retrieve the information without looking at where you wrote it down. Testing yourself to retrieve the

information is better than repeated studying. Practicing retrieval creates more long-term and meaningful learning experiences.

Mnemonic devices can be in the form of acronyms, abbreviations, songs, or rhymes.

Mnemonics have been tested since the 1960s as an effective strategy for students. You've probably been taught a few mnemonic devices for remembering long lists. For example, the colors of the spectrum can be remembered with the name ROY G. BIV (Red, Orange, Yellow, Green, Blue, Indigo, Violet).

Grouping or chunking refers to the process of dividing newly learned information into chunks to produce fewer, larger chunks of information. For example, you may have noticed that it's much easier to remember a phone number if the 10 digits are grouped into three separate chunks (e.g. 555-637-8299) rather than one long number (5556378299).

Diets such as the Mediterranean diet, DASH (dietary approaches to stop hypertension), and the MIND diet (Mediterranean-DASH intervention for neurodegenerative delay) have a few things in common. This includes their ability to improve memory and reduce the risk of Parkinson's and Alzheimer's disease Trusted Source.

These diets focus on eating:

- plant-based foods, especially green, leafy vegetables and berries
- whole grains
- legumes
- nuts
- chicken or turkey
- olive oil or coconut oil
- herbs and spices
- fatty fish, such as salmon and sardines
- red wine, in moderation

Fatty fish are a rich source of omega-3 fatty acids. Omega-3s play an important role in building brain and nerve cells. They're essential for learning and memory and have been shown to delay Trusted Source cognitive decline.

While you should still take your medications prescribed by your doctor, remember to follow your doctor's instructions for dietary and lifestyle changes too.

Some prescriptions, like statins for high cholesterol, have been associated with memory loss and "brain fog." Losing weight and eating healthier may also play a role in treating high cholesterol.

Other medications that might affect memory include:

- antidepressants
- anti-anxiety medications
- hypertension drugs
- sleeping aids
- metformin

Talk to your doctor about how to manage your medical conditions so you don't have to rely on a prescription forever. If you're worried about how a medication may affect your memory, talk to your doctor about your options.

There is research that has found that when something is read out loud, it helps to memorise the materials better. This is often why in school you are encouraged to read out

loud as a group, as it has been proven to teach you new ideas and concepts and improves understanding and recall.

You might feel like you're throwing away valuable learning time by having an early night before an exam, but it can actually improve your memory because sleep is so important for learning and memory. If you were to take a nap after a lecture, then it can help you to remember it better.

As humans we are very much creatures of habit. However, when you mix things up with your studying, it can help your memory. If you only study in your bedroom, how about going to the library next time or just to the kitchen table? If you would normally study late at night, try getting up early and studying in the morning instead. When an element of novelty is added to your studying, then you can make your studying more effective, and improve your recall.

When something you are reading isn't very familiar, it can take you longer to process it. However, if you establish a connection between the new information and something you already know and remember, then it can improve the likelihood of remembering the new information.

A few changes to how you study and how your mind works as you study, can make a big difference to your memory power as a student.

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